

Intrusion Detection System based on Machine Learning : A Review

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Abstract—Internet of Things (IoT) is a new model for integrating physical and virtual objects to connect in concept as anything anywhere and anytime to transmit information via a global network. It is interoperability and heterogenous of many devices that lead to the vulnerability of the IoT network that allows attackers to attack and disrupt the network. Therefore, additional security tools on IoT network in this paper we proposed a common survey the Intrusion Detection System concept and analyzed Intrusion Detection System (IDS) based on Machine Learning could fulfill this purpose.

Keywords—Intrusion Detection System, Machine Learning, Internet of Things, Literature Review

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, Internet of Things (IoT) is a new paradigm that is applied in many applications domain on smart concept such as smart manufacturing/industrial, smart transportation /mobility, smart grid/energy, smart retail, smart agriculture, and smart building/home. They are provided the facility of daily living of people led to the number of devices that connected the internet are being more and the vulnerability for attack on cyber is also increasing. The number of devices that are expected to be connected to internet from the Gartner by 2025 is 75.44 billion [1] and the size of the internet of thing (IoT) security market worldwide from 2016 to 2025, 7.28 to 30.9 billion U.S. dollars[2]. So, the security issues are concerned in the IoT system. The basic security requirements have 6 keys important consist of confidentiality, availability, integrity, non-repudiation, authentication, and privacy [3-8].

The attack is a big problem in the IoT system which two types include passive attacks and active attacks [9-10]. The attack method on the network layer consist of denial of service[11], hello flooding [12], eavesdropping/sniffing[12], man-in-the-middle[13], routing[14], selective forwarding [14], sinkhole[12], spoofing [12], sybil[13], malicious code [8], and traffic analysis[11]. Some of the attack dimension divided to 4 categories consists of denials of service (DoS), probing, remote to local (R2L) and user to root (U2R)

However, currently has a various methods for detecting and preventing the network from the attacker. One of the popular method for detecting and preventing the network from the attacker which addition the high level security is intrusion detection system (IDS) method. But now the IDS must be

improved for a new context of the internet such as Internet of Things (IoT) which is surveyed and analyzed in this paper.

This paper is going to survey the up-to-date intrusion detection system concept and also analyze the intrusion detection system based on machine learning.

II. INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM CONCEPT

Intrusion detection system: a security service that monitors and analyzes system events for the purpose of finding, and providing real-time or near real-time warning of, attempt to access system resources in an unauthorized manner[15]. IDS are often classified by many researchers and different viewpoint such as classified base on position base composed of Host-based IDS, network-based IDS, and Hybrid IDS[15-18]. And classified based on detection-based consists of signature base IDS, and anomaly based IDS.

A. Position based IDS

The position based IDS divided to 3 types:

- 1) *Host-based IDS (HIDS)*: monitors the characteristics of a single host and the events occurring within that host, such as process identifiers and the system calls they make, for evidence of suspicious activity[15].
- 2) *Network-based IDS (NIDS)*: monitors network traffic for particular network segments of devices and analyzes network, transport, and application protocols to identify suspicious activity[15].
- 3) *Hybrid-based IDS*: Both host-based and network-based IDS, can be used at the same time[20].

B. Detection based IDS

The detection based IDS divided to 2 types:

- 1) *Signature based or misuse IDS* : uses a set of known malicious data patterns (signature) or attack rules that are compared with current behavior to decide if it is that of an intruder. it is also known as misuse detection. this approach can only identify known attacks for which it has pattern or rules [15].
- 2) *Anomaly based IDS*: Anomaly detection is the process of finding outliers in a given dataset. Outliers are the data objects that stand out amongst other objects in the dataset and do not conform to the normal behavior in a dataset[19].

III. MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUE FOR INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM

Machine Learning Techniques for IoT IDS consists of supervised learning: naïve baye (NB), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), decision tree (DT), support vector machine (SVM), random forest (RF), ensemble learning (EL), and unsupervised learning: k-mean, principal component analysis (PCA). See Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. A taxonomy of ML Techniques for IoT-based IDSs [40].

They are most popular techniques used for detection intrusion system that monitored and detected the network and report that status normal/anormal. For Example, these technique are applied as brief below:

1) *Naïve Baye (NB)*: NB is a machine learning classification technique base on Baye's Theorem with an assumption of indepedence among predictors. The classifier algorithm was used to model the normal and abnormal network activity[22]. NB is usually used in IoT to detect intrusion detection in the network layer, and anomaly detection. NB has some advantages, such as simple to understand, requiring less data for classification, easy to implement, applicable for multi-stage[10].

2) *K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN)*: KNN technique does not require any parameter in supervised learning which usually uses Euclidian distance. Euclidian distance in KNN determines the average value of unknown node which is k nearest neighbors. KNN method is used in intrusion detection, malware detections, and anomaly detection in IoT. KNN algorithm is simple, cheap, and easy to apply. In contrast, it is a time-consuming process to identify the missing nodes which are challenging in terms of accuracy [10].

3) *Decision Tree (DT)*: DT is mainly categorized as classification and regression. DT has advantages over other ML techniques like simple construction, easy to implement that handling large data samples. DT are widely used as classifier in security applications like DoS and intrusion detection [10].

4) *Support Vector Machine (SVM)*: The algorithm is used to analyze data that use regression and classification analysis. SVM possesses a high accuracy level which makes it suitable for security application in IoT like intrusion detection, malware detection, etc. [10]. SVM are ideal for anomaly detection where classification between normal and abnormal class is required [21].

5) *Random Forest (RF)*: The method that combines the decision trees and ensemble learning. The prediction is decided by majority voting. This mechanism can be applied for improved the performance of IDS [23]. Used in DDoS attack detection, anomaly detection, an unauthorized IoT devices identification in network layer etc.

6) *Ensemble Learning (EL)*: Used for anomaly detection, malware detection, and intrusion detection. EL use difference classification techniques to get an acceptable outcome by increasing its performance [10].

7) *K-Mean*: The clustering method base on unsupervised learning. Which is usually used in anomaly detection and Sybil attack detection on IoT system [10].

8) *Principal Component Analysis (PCA)*: Which is also know as a feature reduction technique converts a large data set into smaller ones. It decrease the complexity of a system. This method used for selecting a feature to detect real-time intrusion attacks in an IoT system. The combination of PCA and some other ML methods can be applied to provide a strong security protocol [10].

IV. ANALYZED THE EXISTING IDS WITH MACHINE LEARNING

This section analyzed the existing intrusion detection system with machine learning from 17 research papers. These can be classified to 7 aspects as follow and show some details in Table I.

1) Techniques and type composed of a single algorithm [33-39] and combine algorithm or multiple method [10, 24-32]

2) Dataset, The most of the dataset that use are KDDcup99 and NSL_KDD

3) Attack categories consists of Denials of Service (DoS), Probing, Remote to Local (R2L) and User to Root (U2R)

4) Performance consists of accuracy, precision, recall, f-measure, detection rate, computation time, and false positive.

5) Detection base for all of anomaly detection

6) Benchmark are compared with other algorithm (method/model) and compared with the other datasets

7) The reasons for improve the method for IDS consist of Traditional security mechanisms are not appropriate for IoT networks, because the IoT platforms cover regular internet, non-IP network, mobile network, cloud computing, fog computing, and sensor network. IoT devices also have limited processing and memory capability [24], existing anomalous intrusion detection models often misclassified normal network traffics as attacks while minority attacks go undetected due to extreme an imbalance in network traffic data. The leads to high false positive and low detection rate [25], Traditional classifiers shown the poor performance, now there is no standard model and datasets are available for evaluating the IDS [27], Lightweight techniques with less complexity, low resource usage and low computation requirement are necessary. The development of such techniques remains a challenging research task [28], the network behavior intrusion or normal base on the collection data of network status which high dimension and linear inseparable. In order to improved accuracy of network intrusion detection [29].

TABLE I. THE EXISTING INTRUSION DETECTION MODEL BASE ON MACHINE LEARNING

Paper NO, Year	Technique Name	Type	Performance	Dataset	Attacks Categories	Benchmark
[33], 2018	Decision Tree	Single	guarantee accuracy	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with two method
[34], 2017	KNN	Single	high accuracy	NSL-KDD	DOS, Prob	Compared with tradition KNN
[35], 2018	K-Mean/Random forest	Combine	improve false positive	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with many cluster dataset
[36], 2020	Support Vector Machine	Single	Increases the accuracy and minimizes the false alarm rate.	NSL-KDD	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Challenge Complex Environment such as cloud computing
[37], 2020	Naïve bayes	Single	improve accuracy	NSL_KDD	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared to other models.
[38], 2019	Random Forest	Single	accuracy, precision, recall, f-measure	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with different features
[39], 2017	K-Mean	Single	detection rate, false detection rate	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Improved k-mean algorithm
[10], 2020	Decision Tree, Random Forest	Combine	high accuracy, precision	NSL-KDD CICIDS2017	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compare with other dataset
[24], 2020	Decision Tree, Random Forest	Combine	lowest false positive accuracy, Precision, recall, f-score	IoT Botnet	DoS ,DoS, Reconnaissance, Theft	Compared with KDD, UNSW-NB15, CICIDS2017
[25], 2019	K-Mean, Random Forest	Combine	higher detection accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with existing model
[26], 2019	PCA, Naïve Bayes, K-Nearest	Combine	higher detection rate, low false positive accuracy	NSL-KDD	R2L, U2R	Compared with existing model
[27], 2017	Ensemble SVM Rough set theory (RST)	Combine	increase the detection accuracy and reduces the computation time	KDDCUP'99 UNB-ISCX HTTP CSIC	-	Enhances the detection rate and decreases the detection time
[28], 2018	Principle Component Analysis Level 1-2	Combine	Reduce the complexity, and Increase the detection rate	Kyoto HoneyPot	-	Compared with different dataset
[29], 2017	Random Forest, Support Vector Machine	Combine	higher detection rate	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with Other algorithm
[30], 2017	Principle Component Analysis, Soft max regression, K-Nearest Neighbors	Combine	low computing complexity, low memory size, high accuracy	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with different number of features
[31], 2016	K-Means, Naïve bayes	Combine	improve detection rate	KDDCUP99	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with other model
[32], 2019	Naïve bayes , Random Forest K-Nearest Neighbor, J-48	Combine	high accuracy low false positive	NSL-KDD	DOS, Prob, R2L, U2R	Compared with other model

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper , we present a literature review of intrusion detection system base on machine learning, including of three things: First, intrusion detection system concept. The second, one is machine learning technique for intrusion detection system. Finally, analyzed the existing intrusion detection model base on machine learning. The knowledge from the analysis will provided direction for the researcher to develop and improve the IDS base on machine learning for support the new paradigm Internet of things network.

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